

Spectrophotometric determination of submicrogram amount of zinc with 5-(2'-carbomethoxyphenyl)azo-8-quinolinol in the anionic micellar medium of sodium dodecylsulfate

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Anionic micellar medium of sodium dodecylsulfate is utilized to solubilize the insoluble complex of zinc formed with 5-(2'-carbomethoxyphenyl)azo-8-quinolinol in aqueous medium at pH 4.0–4.8. The dissolution of the complex results in an orange-red colour stable for 4 h and is proposed as a novel method for the determination of zinc at submicrogram level. The colour obeys Beer's law in the range 0–0.42 μg of zinc per ml at 488 nm and has molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity $4.14 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1.57 ng cm^{-2} respectively. The limit of determination and quantitation are 0.20 and 0.80 ppm in rock samples.

Although methods for the determination of zinc with zincon are becoming more common, the well established method with dithizone continues to be favourite¹. But the method requires addition of sodium thiosulphate to improve its selectivity as the reagent forms extractable coloured complexes with nearly 20 metals. This makes the method empirical due to formation of a weak complex with zinc, use of extremely pure reagent etc. to avoid high and erratic blank, use of subdued light for just sufficient time, and absence of any oxidizing agent to avoid formation of intense yellow coloured diphenylthiocarbodiazone soluble in organic solvents. The zincon method, though free from these problems, has relatively poor sensitivity and selectivity.

In continuation of our analytical work on the applicability of 5-azoxine derivatives, we report here a highly sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of zinc using 5-(2'-carbomethoxyphenyl)azo-8-quinolinol as a reagent in presence of an anionic surfactant sodium dodecylsulfate (NaDDS) which solubilizes the zinc complex probably by hydrophobic interaction². The solubilization results in an orange-red colour and avoids the need of extraction.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra reveal a red-shift of the absorption maximum (460 nm) for the reagent by 28 nm due to complex formation, resulting the complex peak at 488 nm. The peak is found to be independent of pH in the range 4.0–4.8. A pH of 4.5 was arbitrarily selected and a sodium acetate-

acetic acid buffer solution was used to adjust the pH for subsequent studies.

The interaction between the reagent (R) and zinc in aqueous medium at pH 4.0–4.8 resulted in an insoluble complex. The solubilization of the complex was affected by addition of suitable surfactant. The non-ionic surfactant like triton X-100 did not dissolve the precipitate indicating its ionic nature. The exact nature of the complex could not be ascertained as the cationic surfactants, viz. cetylpyridinium chloride and tetradecyltrimethylammoniumbromide did not dissolve the complex and resulted in disappearance of the colour due to the formation of insoluble zinc complex by breaking the Zn-R complex probably due to presence of pyridinium and ammonium ions in them respectively. The anionic surfactants NaDDS, labolene (a phosphate-free, arylalkylsulfonate, neutral in nature; Qualigens) and extran MK-01 (containing some neutral surfactant and phosphate, alkaline in nature; E. Merck) were tried and all of these solubilized the insoluble Zn-R complex probably due to hydrophobic interaction³. As the exact composition of labolene and extran MK-01 was not known, the subsequent studies were made using NaDDS.

The effect of surfactant concentration was determined by measuring the absorbance at 488 nm of a set of solutions containing increasing amount of NaDDS (2.0×10^{-2} to 1.6×10^{-1} %), and fixed amounts of metal ion, R and buffer. The increasing concentration of NaDDS increased the solubilization of Zn-R complex. In the concentration range 7.6×10^{-2} to 8.4×10^{-2} %, the Zn-R complex was ob-

served to be completely soluble resulting in clear solution, and was confirmed by maximal absorbance of the solution. The NaDDS concentrations higher than $8.4 \times 10^{-2} \%$ resulted in slight decrease in the absorbance. The effect of reagent (R) concentration was studied in the range 4×10^{-6} to $8 \times 10^{-5} M$. The optimum absorbance of the complex coupled with minimum blank absorbance was found with $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ R. The molar ratio and continuous variation methods showed formation of 2 : 1 ligand-to-metal complex.

The effect of various diverse ion was studied setting the criterion as $\pm 2\%$ change in the absorbance for 0.042 ppm of zinc. Milligram amounts of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and acetate did not interfere in the determination of 0.042 ppm of Zn^{2+} . $250 \mu\text{g}$ of Cr^{VI} and F^- and $125 \mu\text{g}$ of Mn^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} each were tolerated. Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mo^{VI} did not interfere. Interference due to Ag^+ was removed by adding chloride and filtering prior to determination. However, Hg^{2+} and Cd^{2+} interfered seriously.

Seven replicate determination with 0.042 ppm of Zn^{2+} gave coefficient of variation as $\pm 0.8\%$.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements with 10 mm matched quartz cuvettes.

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. 5-(2'-Carbomethoxyphenyl)azo-8-quinolinol was synthesized according to

the reported method³. A $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent (R) solution was prepared in 1 M HCl and diluting with water to 100 ml. Stock solutions of $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ NaDDS and 0.01 M zinc sulphate were prepared.

To a suitable aliquot containing 0–10.5 μg of zinc, solutions of NaDDS (2 ml), sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (10 ml) of pH 4.5 and R (1 ml) were added and the volume was made up to 25 ml. Its absorbance was measured after 0.5 h at 488 nm against the reagent blank.

In case the sample containing Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Mo^{VI} , the pH was adjusted to 5.5–6.5 with dilute nitric acid and ammonia. It was mixed with 0.05% acetone solution of R (1 ml) and MIBK (5 ml) and shaken for 1 min. The organic phase was discarded and the estimation of zinc was carried out in aqueous phase as described above.

The method was applied for the determination of zinc in water samples, bore-well water by standard spacing at levels < 25 ppb and the results compared well with that determined by AAS method.

References

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